

STRATEGY IMPLEMENTATION AND PERFORMANCE OF SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES IN EKITI STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study investigated the effects of strategy implementation practices on performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined the effects of policy manual, development and implementation, financial resources, staff motivation, organizational structure and willingness to accept change on performance of small and medium enterprises in Ekiti State. Primary data were used for the study and were collected using a well-structured questionnaire. The study was essentially descriptive and exploratory in nature. A sample size of 383 was selected from the population of 9,275 registered and active small and medium enterprises in the selected six local government areas (LGAs) in Ekiti State, Nigeria. From each of the six previously selected LGAs; 96, 36, 60, 62, 46 and 83 SMEs respectively were selected using proportionate sampling technique. Frequency count, percentages and structural equation modelling of partial least square (SEM-PLS) were adopted for the data analyses. Findings from the study establishes that policy manual, development and implementation, financial resources, staff motivation, organizational structure and willingness to accept change have positive and significant effect on performance of SMEs in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study concluded that increase in strategy implementation is sin-qua-non to the survival and performance of small and medium enterprises in Nigeria. The study therefore recommends an improvement in small business owners and managers' strategic thinking and formulation with a view to putting in place appropriate strategies that will enhance SMEs' performances particularly in developing countries.

Keywords: Corporate Strategy, Strategy Formulation, Strategy Implementation, Organisational Performance, Small and Medium Enterprises, Resource-Based View Theory

I. Introduction

Organisations either private or public are increasingly embracing the practice of strategic management in anticipation that this would translate to improved performance. The harsh economic condition in Nigeria occasioned by Federal government economic policies which include floating of Naira, deregulation of oil and gas sector, removal of oil subsidy and devaluation of Nigerian currency (naira) is taking its toll on businesses in Nigeria especially small enterprises. The unfriendly economic policies of federal government in Nigeria particularly in the last ten years has led to relocation of transnational companies such as Michelin and Dunlop from Nigeria to neighbouring countries and many are threatening to leave. This has led to increase in unemployment rate in the country. Many employable able bodied youths and tertiary institutions' graduates who could not secure jobs either in the public or private sector have devised means of survival by starting their own small businesses. Unfortunately the un-supporting government policies and taxes, and keen competition are impacting negatively on their survival and profitability. Only those small businesses who embraced strategic management through appropriate strategy formulation and implementation will be able to have a headway. The success of every strategy is its implementation which is closely linked with organizational success. This brings to fore the strategic role of strategy implementation in organizational performance.

Literature indicate that about 80% of Nigerian SMEs fail within their first five years of operation due to weak management strategies and poor entrepreneurial orientation [1]. Several studies on SMEs in Nigeria have been conducted on different aspect of management and not specifically on assessing the effects of strategy implementation on performance of SMEs in Ekiti State, Nigeria. For instance, studies by [2] and [3] focused primarily on financial constraints, regulatory challenges and market conditions of SMEs. Also, [4] Onikoyi, et al. (2021) studied strategic management and organisational performance in Cadbury Nigeria Plc., which is a transnational corporation. [5] conducted a study on strategic management practices, decision making styles and performance of small and medium enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria. These studies did not address specifically the possible effects strategy implementation may have on performance especially of Small and medium enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria thereby making the present study to stand out.

Critically looking at the various methodologies used by the previous studies, it was observed that majority of the studies [4]; [6]; [7]; [8] conducted in recent time have used majorly regression analysis while [5] used a mix of multiple regression and logit; [9] employed Pearson's bivariate correlation, multiple regression and moderated regression analysis; [10] used both quantile regression and hierarchical regression; [11] adopted a mix of Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient (PPMC), One Way Analysis of Variance (Anova) and Simple Regression. However, the present study intends to use Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS) which is perceived to be a stronger analytical technique capable of generating more robust results for the type of comprehensive data to be collected. It also helps to analyse complex relationship between variables. SEM-PLS is a sophisticated statistical tool that enables researchers to explore but also to analyse the relationship between observed variables and underlying latent construct [12].

In view of the above, this study seeks to examine how strategy implementation practices influence the growth and sustainability of SMEs in Ekiti State. By exploring the relationship between this factor and SMEs' performance, this study will provide valuable insights for business owners, policymakers, and stakeholders on how to improve SMEs success rates and enhance economic development in the region.

This raises the question of "to what extent will strategy implementation affects performance of SMEs in Ekiti State, Nigeria?" On this basis, the study hypothesized that strategy formulation has no significant effect on performance of SMEs in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

I. Materials and Methods

A. Literature Review

1. Corporate Strategy

Andrews in [20] defined corporate strategy as the pattern of major objectives, purposes or goals, and essential policies and plans for achieving those goals stated in such a way as to define what business the company is into or is to engage in. Steiner and Miller in [13] posited that strategy is the formulation of company's vision, mission, and setting of objectives and the development of actions to achieve the objectives. Corporate strategy is therefore the art and science of formulating, implementing and evaluating cross-functional objectives.

Strategic implementation is an aspect of strategic management. According to [14], strategic management is a continuous process of evaluating and controlling the business and the industries in which it operates, assessing its competitors, setting goals and strategies to meet all existing and potential rivals, and then reassessing each strategy in the light of charged circumstances or a new economic environment or a new social, financial or political environment. It is a bunch of choices and activities which result in the formulation and implementation of plans intended to accomplish an organization's goals [5]). Strategy implementation is one of the processes of strategic management - which involves strategic thinking, analysis, planning, formulation, implementation, and evaluation and control

2. Strategy Formulation

The process of developing a company's strategy is known as strategy formulation. Identifying a company's strengths helps in strategy development. Strategy formulation is the development of long range plans for the effective management of environmental opportunities and threats in the light of corporate strengths and weaknesses. It includes defining the corporate mission, specifying achievable objectives, developing strategies and setting policy guidelines. It begins with situational analysis.

In strategy formulation, firm define their overall long-term direction and scope; and establish the way they will create value, by configuring their activities and resources. Strategy formulation is thus a deliberate exercise to develop a company's competitive advantage and thus enhance its performance (Gimbert et al. in [15]). However, the extent to which a firm's goals are achieved relies on their strategy implementation expertise.

3. Strategy Implementation

Strategy implementation is concerned with the activities and efforts exerted to activate a strategy that has been formulated to enable the firm achieve its goals. The role of strategy implementation in improving performance of organizations has been a discourse of interest to scholars; and several studies have been conducted on the subject [16]; [15].

Implementing a strategy entails putting it into action. Steps, methods, and procedures for putting the strategy into action are all included in the implementation. It comprises deciding which strategies should be put into practice first. It's important to prioritize strategies according to how serious the underlying issues are. To begin with, the organization should focus on the most pressing issues, and then move on to the rest. When strategies are being developed, it is important to think about how they will be implemented [17]. When formulating new strategies, the business should think about how those plans will be put into action and steps to be taking to ensure they enhance organizational success. This is the most basic part of strategic management. It includes the day by day choices made on how assets are assigned. Strategy implementation is concerned with the day-to-day activities of managing the strategy to achieve the strategic goals of the organization [15]. Thus, once plans are developed, they must be actively managed and implemented to maintain the momentum of the strategy. Strategy implementation involves organisation of the firm's resources and motivation of the staff to achieve objectives. Strategy implementation is one of the critical elements of strategic management, which has to do with translating strategy into actions. It's the phase of the translation of strategies into action.

The three major approaches to the implementation of strategies involve procedures, budgets, and programs. It is acknowledged by [18], that procedures are sequential techniques or steps of a system that gives a detailed explanation of each program. A budget serves as a financial summary of a company's various initiatives. A budget is used for planning and control, and it lists the specific costs associated with each program. While a program is a statement of the activities or steps needed to accomplish a single-use plan. It is the orientation of the strategy.

Corroborating this, [16] conducted a study on the role of strategy implementation in the relationship between strategic planning systems and performance in Sudan. The study adopted a descriptive cross-sectional survey with the firm as the unit of analysis. The outcome of the multiple regression analysis indicated that strategy implementation moderates the relationship between strategic planning systems and market performance as well as internal business process performance but not on return on investment performance. [19] conducted a study on successful strategic plan implementation in public organizations: connecting people, process, and plan (3Ps). The study provides evidence-based recommendations from strategic plans initiatives in Flemish municipalities, Belgium using multi-informant and multisource survey data in Flemish municipalities. The outcomes of the structural equation modelling (SEM) revealed that successfully implementing strategic plans is influenced by the people, process, and plan. A related study by [15] examined the effect of strategy implementation on organizational performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study concentrated on top and middle level management level staff at the Headquarters of Zenith Bank Plc. Access Bank, Guaranty Trust Bank, First Bank Plc. and United Bank of Africa Plc. The study adopted descriptive research design with a population of 252 and 205. Questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection and simple regression was used to analyze the collected data. The findings of the study revealed a significant statistical relationship between strategy implementation and prompt service

delivery. It was also revealed that, there is a significant statistical relationship between strategy implementation and customer satisfaction.

B. Organizational Performance

In the views of [20] organizational performance is the outcome of all of the organization's operations and strategies. The cornerstone for developing strategic plans and assessing an organization's accomplishment of objectives and goals is performance measurement systems [21]. Firms that perform well are more likely to remain in business, which can be divided into two categories: financial and business performance [21]. The core of an organization's efficacy is its financial performance. Using accounting-based metrics like return on assets and return on equity, financial success is measured. Market share, performance, diversification, and product development are some of the metrics that are used to measure business performance in the context of the marketplace [20]. Organizational performance is an abstract concept; and is difficult to measure directly. Firms therefore select indirect indices to represent it [22]. However, the most frequently used measures of organizational performance include market share, customer satisfaction, profitability, productivity, cost minimization and business development.

Past studies such as [23] have used diverse indicators to measure firm performance. These indicators can be grouped into two which are financial and non-financial performance. Financial performance measures have been mostly used as compared to non-financial performance measures. Financial performance measures include profit before tax, profit per employee, growth in revenue, and growth in number of employees. Non-financial performance measures are customers' satisfaction, customers' referral rate, growth in customers' base, and market share. In this study, performance is measured in terms of profitability, market share and customer satisfaction.

C. Small and Medium Enterprises

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) have been recognized all over the world as the engine of growth in modern economies due to their significant contribution to global economic growth and sustainable development through employment generation, poverty alleviation, wealth creation and food security. The term Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) has no generally established definition. Small and medium scale enterprise, small scale industries, and small-scale enterprises are used interchangeably to mean a small-scale industry firm.

The criteria for classification of an enterprise as small, medium or large varies from one country to another, depending on whether it is a developed or developing country. In Nigeria, the major criteria used in defining Small and medium Enterprises (SMEs) include number of employees, financial strength, sales value, initial capital outlay, relative size, independent ownership and the type of industry. In view of the above criteria, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) in its monetary policy circular No 22 of 1988 defined small-scale enterprises as having an annual turnover not exceeding five hundred thousand naira [24]. While the Federal Ministry of Industries in 1973 [24] defined small scale enterprises as businesses that have total capital (land, building machinery equipment and working capital) of up to N60, 000 and employ up to 50 persons. The Federal Ministry of Industries defines a medium-scale enterprise as any company with operating assets less than ₦200 million and employing less than 300 persons. A small-scale enterprise, on the other hand, is one that has total assets of less than ₦50 million, with less than 100 employees. Annual turnover will not be considered in the definition of an SME [25]; [26].

D. Resource-Based View Theory

The theoretical foundation of this study is the resource-based view theory. The resource-based view of the firm (RBV) is one of the most widely accepted theoretical perspectives used to explain strategic management. RBV theory focuses on the collection of firm resources and capabilities [27]. The theory suggests that the resources possessed by a firm are the primary determinants of its performance, and these may contribute to a sustainable competitive advantage of the firm. The resource-based view advocates that competitive advantage and performance results are a consequence of firm-specific resources and capabilities that are costly to copy by other competitors. The resource-based view (RBV) is a means to determine strategic resources of the organization and how it affects its performance based mainly on reviewing its internal environment. A firm using RBV is able to compete in terms of its resources and capabilities of which is the strategy formulation and implementation.

II. Methodology

Primary data used for the study were collected with the aid of a semi-structured questionnaire. The study was essentially descriptive in nature. The population of the study comprises 9,275 registered and active small and medium enterprises in the selected local government areas (LGAs) in Ekiti State, Nigeria as reported by the Ministry of trade, industry, investment and cooperatives, Ekiti State in 2023 in [28]. The sample size for the study was 383 and was calculated using Yamane (1967). Multi-stage sampling technique was used to draw the representative sample for the study. Using cluster sampling technique, two Local Government Areas (LGAs) from each of the three senatorial district in Ekiti State with the highest concentration of SMEs were selected, making six (6) LGAs altogether. From each of the six (6) previously selected LGAs 96, 36, 60, 62, 46 and 83 SMEs respectively were selected using proportionate sampling technique, totaling 383. Frequency count and percentages were used to analysed respondents' demographic variables while structural equation modelling of partial least square (SEM-PLS) was employed to test the hypothesis generated for the study.

A. Model Specification

$$\eta = B_0 + L\eta + \varepsilon \dots\dots\dots eq1$$

Where η represent endogenous variables, η is a vector of exogenous variables, ε is the error or disturbance term vector, and B and L are the regression coefficients of endogenous and exogenous variables.

Mathematically, the model can further be expressed as:

$$SI=f(PCM, ROP, SPD, SSI, MSI, OGS, WAC)\dots\dots\dots eq2$$

Furthermore, the model is expanded as:

$$SF= \beta_0 +L_1PCM+L_2ROP+L_3SPD+L_4SSI+L_5MSI+L_6OGS+L_7WAC \dots\dots\dots eq3$$

Where:

SI= Strategy Implementation

PCM= Policy Manual

ROP= Relevance of Policy

SPD= Support for Policy Development

SIS= Support for Strategy Implementation

MSI= Motivation for Strategy Implementation

OGS= Organisational Structure

WAC= Willingness to Accept Change

β_0 = Constant

L_1 - L_7 = Gradient

B. A-priori Expectations

It is expected that all the proxies of strategy implementation (SMP_i) would have a positive and significant effect on performance of SMEs in terms of profitability, market share and customer satisfaction. Mathematically, the *a-priori* expectations is expressed thus:

$\frac{dPFT}{dSMP_i} > 0$: this connotes that all the proxies of strategy implementation would exert a positive effect on profitability.

$\frac{dMKS}{dSMP_i} > 0$: this connotes that all the proxies of strategy implementation would exert a positive effect on market share.

$\frac{dCSA}{dSMP_i} > 0$: this connotes that all the proxies of strategy implementation would exert a positive effect on customer satisfaction.

III. Results and Discussion

A. Results

Table 1 presents socio-demographic indicators. There were more males (57.7%) than females (43.3%), and more than 60% of the sample were aged 30 to 49 years. According to marital status, 45% of the sample was married while the rest were single, divorced, separated or widowed. The majority of participants studied up to the ordinary diploma level (60%), while the rest held higher diploma levels and degrees (40%).

Table I: Descriptive Statistics for Sociodemographic Indicators.

Variables	n (%)
N	383
Sex	
Male	221 (57.7)
Female	162 (42.3)
Age category	
25-29 years	64 (16.7)
30-39 years	127 (33.2)
40-49 years	120 (31.3)
50-59 years	61 (15.9)
60 years and over	11 (2.9)
Marital status	
Single	102 (26.6)
Married	172 (44.9)
Divorced	62 (16.2)
Widowed/Widower	38 (9.9)
Separated	9 (2.3)
Education	
Primary	71 (18.5)
O'level	75 (19.6)
ND	84 (21.9)
HND	108 (28.2)
BSc.	24 (6.3)
Masters	21 (5.5)
	M (SD)
Strategic implementation	5.12 (0.67)
Performance	5.14 (0.78)

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Table 2 presents composite reliability (CR) and construct validity indices. The CRs for all measures (.75 to .87) were above the threshold of .60 [29], suggesting that all the study measures are reliable. In addition, there was evidence of discriminant validity, given that the square roots of the AVE, ranging from .71 to .75, were greater than the inter-construct correlations (.32 to .61). Convergent validity was established for all the latent constructs as their AVEs (.51 to .57) were greater than the threshold of .50 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Table II: Construct validity, reliability, and inter-construct correlations

Variables	CR	AVE	MSV	MaxR(H)	ER	SF	SI	EIN	PER
Strategic formulation (SF)	0.87	0.57	0.15	0.895	0.24	0.76			
Strategic implementation (SI)	0.83	0.55	0.15	0.841	0.37	0.38	0.74		
Performance (PER)	0.75	0.51	0.37	0.763	0.61	0.32	0.37	0.55	0.71

Note. AVE = Average variance extracted; MaxR(H) = Maximum reliability; CR = Composite reliability; † = Square root of AVE; MSV = maximum shared variance; The square root of the AVE is in bold

1. Test of Hypothesis: There is no significant effect of strategy implementation on the performance of SMEs in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

SEM analysis was used to test hypothesis 2. Figs. 1a and 1b display the path models with standardised estimates, including or excluding the CLF, respectively. Performance was regressed onto strategic implementation while controlling for gender, age, marital status and education. The model achieved the acceptable criteria for fitness: $\chi^2(33) = 73.11, p < .001$; SRMR = .04; CFI = .97 and RMSEA = .06 [90% CI = (.04, .08)].

Fig. 1a: Predicting performance from strategic implementation
Source: Data Analysis, 2025

Fig. 1a shows that strategy implementation significantly predicted SMEs performance ($\beta = .36, p < .001$). However, the inclusion of the CLF in Figure 3b indicates that strategy implementation is not truly predictive of SMEs performance ($\beta = .01, p = .97$). This implies that the significant relationship between strategy implementation and performance was accounted for by common method bias. Therefore, there is no true significant relationship between the two variables. Gender, age, marital status, and education were not significant in the model.

Fig. 1b: Predicting performance from implementation controlling for CLF
Source: Data Analysis, 2025

B. Discussion

The study establishes a positive and significant relationship between strategy implementation and SMEs' Performance. The outcome of the study corroborated the results of the research conducted by [5] on strategic management practices, decision making styles and performance of small and medium enterprises in Ekiti State, Nigeria using strategic implementation as a proxy. Their study indicated a positive and significant effect of strategy implementation on performance of SMEs in Ekiti State. Also, the study confirmed the findings of a related study by [17] on the role of strategy implementation in the relationship between strategic planning systems and performance in Sudan. The outcome of the study indicated that strategy implementation moderates the relationship between strategic planning systems and market

performance as well as internal business process performance but not on return on investment performance. Similarly, the study was in line with the outcome of the study by [30] on strategic planning and implementation success in public service organizations: evidence from Canada. Findings of the research indicated that formal strategic planning has a strong positive relationship with implementation, which, though mediated by managerial involvement, becomes even more salient in the face of stakeholder uncertainty.

In addition, this study corroborates the findings of the work of [20] on successful strategic plan implementation in public organizations: connecting people, process, and plan (3Ps). The results of the study revealed that successful implementation of strategic plans was influenced by the people, process, and plan (3Ps) and that high-quality strategic plans contribute to successful strategic plan implementation. Furthermore, the outcome of this study supported a related research conducted by [16] which examined the effect of strategy implementation on organizational performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The findings of the study revealed that, there was a significant statistical relationship between strategy implementation and prompt service delivery. It was also revealed that, there was a significant statistical relationship between strategy implementation and customer satisfaction.

IV. Conclusion and Managerial Implications

Based on the outcome of the study, it was concluded that appropriate strategy implementation led to a significant increase in performance of small and medium enterprises. Organisation's policy manual, development and implementation, financial resources, staff motivation, organizational structure and willingness to accept change have positive and significant effect on performance of SMEs in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study therefore recommends an improvement in small business owners and managers' strategic thinking and formulation with a view to putting in place appropriate strategies that will enhance SMEs' performances particularly in developing countries.

This study is expository and therefore implied that the owners, managers and employees of small and medium enterprises need to engage in serious strategic thinking, formulation and implementation if they are to succeed. Also all managers and employees should be involved in strategy implementation because laudable ideas may fail if it is poorly implemented. Putting in place policy manual, adherence to its implementation, staff motivation, appropriate organizational structure and willingness of owners, managers and employees to accept change which may be internally or externally induced is sine qua non to SMEs success. Also appropriate policy guidance must be put in place by government and the agencies saddled with the responsibilities of overseeing the activities of small and medium enterprises if they are to succeed and fulfil their roles of enhancing economic development and job creation.

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